

**PRACTICE IN GEOGRAPHIC DISCIPLINES – ONE OF THE MOST IMPORTANT
FORMS OF PEDAGOGICAL EDUCATION
PRACTICA LA DISCIPLINELE GEOGRAFICE – UNA DIN CELE MAI IMPORTANTE
FORME DE EDUCAȚIE PEDAGOGICĂ**

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Abstract: *Field applications serve as an indispensable necessity for the preparation of geographic specialists either for the preparation of a pedagogical profile, either for preparation of the research and administration of some objectives, for the protection of the natural or anthropic resources. The present article highlights some of the most important geographical objectives existing within the central - western and southwestern area of Moldova, where field applications can be performed.*

Keywords: *applications, indispensable, specialists, objectives, geographical*

Rezumat: *Aplicațiile de teren servesc drept o necesitate indispensabilă pentru pregătirea specialiștilor geografi fie de profil pedagogic sau de cercetare și administrare a unor obiective de protecție a patrimoniului resurselor naturale sau antropice. Prezenta lucrare scoate în evidență unele din importante obiective geografice existente în cadrul spațiului geografic, din zona central-vestică și sud-vestică a Republicii Moldova, unde se poate efectua aplicații de teren la disciplinele de geografie.*

Cuvinte-cheie: *aplicații, indispensabil, specialist, obiective, geografic*

The training of teaching staff for obtaining the teaching license in Geography disciplines within pedagogical profile universities is conducted in accordance with the existing curriculum plans.

In the current conditions, an essential element in the training process of future professionals in the field of geography is the preparation and implementation of field applications throughout the training and education period. It is worth noting that not all higher education institutions allocate sufficient time to this applied field process, reflected in comprehensive preparation for the accumulation of skills and practical experience related to both the natural and anthropic components of Geography in general.

This paper aims to highlight the most important forms of organization and implementation of field practices, starting from introductory disciplines in the first year and concluding with those in the fourth year. These practices can, in fact, exhibit continuity for specific specialization profiles and within the master's degree program (cycle II).

Field applications represent an indispensable condition when the theoretical material accumulated within certain disciplines transforms into practical cognitive knowledge applications, under the guidance of specialized experts.

An eloquent example serves the understanding and consolidation of knowledge obtained within field applications in physical geography disciplines such as hydrology, pedology, geology, climatology, topography, and cartography. These disciplines are considered the fundamental substrate that allows the future specialist to strengthen their

knowledge about the components of the natural and anthropic geographical environment.

In this context, it is worth mentioning that the best specialists in the mentioned fields are those within the academic and public administrative environment, who can be engaged in field application processes to transmit practical knowledge.

The geographic social-human or economic component can be visualized and analyzed by the student based on specific variables presented both theoretically and practically in disciplines such as human settlement geography, regional human geography, transportation geography, agriculture geography, etc.

Field applications in practice provide optimal conditions for understanding and consolidating the knowledge acquired in theoretical courses, simultaneously representing the necessary framework for developing the skills and abilities required for a geography specialist.

Simultaneously, this form of organizational management, at the level of complex general geography, represents the most effective way of fostering civic responsibility towards the natural and anthropic heritage of the country. It involves the protection, conservation, and rational utilization through sustainable use of existing resources within the geographical environment.

An important element for conducting field applications is the planning of the time allocated for specific objectives subjected to analysis and practical research, as well as covering distances within certain itineraries.

Typically, field applications are planned for the summer and last for a maximum of 10 days, covering various routes in the northern, central, and southern regions of the Republic of Moldova. Students are introduced to various natural and anthropic landscapes, enabling them to distinguish between different landscape zones based on geographic location. During field applications, visual descriptions are provided, and subsequently, based on existing statistical data, some industrial and agricultural complexes are analyzed. Special attention is given to the analysis of rural and urban settlements by their position, area, and population. The population's access to various socio-economic, cultural, educational objectives is identified through connections to different infrastructures and transportation networks. Each student is equipped with the necessary tools to record information, including a portfolio to store, analyze, and visualize events through photo-digital images for each day, which can be processed under laboratory conditions, etc.

Within the field applications, practical analysis of geographical objectives is envisaged to develop skills in differentiating, at a structural-hierarchical level, some natural ecosystems and geosystems. This includes describing landscapes at the level of taxonomic units, such as the existence of geomorphology, geocorology, and geofacies, among others.

The relief forms within anthropic and natural landscapes are highlighted through video-photo montages during applications, which will be further clarified through the creation of topographic maps using existing equipment.

Field activities also encompass the research of climatic elements, such as the description and analysis of hydrometeorological centers.

Individual activities include:

- Processing materials and information obtained in laboratory conditions;
- Creating graphic materials using statistical research methods as well as comparative methods;
- Working with specialized maps, including the development of new plans and topographic maps;
- Analyzing data obtained in the field through overlay and comparison with existing data;
- Creating a portfolio for each objective;
- Compiling a general report, elucidating the formation of a positive attitude towards the role and place of geography in the societal evolution process, with a focus on the protection and rational use of natural and anthropic components of the environment.

Organization and Implementation of Practical Field Applications in Complex General Geography can be structured in three stages:

- The first preparatory stage may involve several actions:
 - Defining the concept of practical field applications at the level of complex geographic disciplines;
 - Determining the practical routes;
 - Establishing collaboration agreements between the Faculty Administration and the institutions and enterprises to be visited, etc.;
 - Providing training to students who will carry out the practical field applications;
 - Communicating the practical routes and the requirements to be fulfilled during the process, including the timeframe and accommodation and catering conditions.
- The second stage involves the actual implementation of the internship.

As a model for field applications, in this paper, we have relied on organizing the geographical expedition within the protected area (PA) of Pădurea Domnească.

Description of the route with mandatory stops (identifying the localities and their specific characteristics through which the bus travels). Within the natural complex of Pădurea Domnească, students can familiarize themselves with the landscape in question, considering its geographical position and the surface area accessible to the public. Students will become acquainted with the multitude of plant species, which actually represent the habitat of various areas of trees and shrubs with regional distribution.

A particular interest for students can be represented by the national architectural landscapes of houses through their exterior and interior design within specific settlements. The material subjected to analysis by students can be systematized based on photo-landscapes. The time allocated for the analysis of this objective can be framed within two days.

Another mandatory objective for the proposed field application visit may include the Hydrometeorological Station within the settlement of Cornești. Students become acquainted with the infrastructure of the station, equipped with modern equipment for estimating air temperature at various heights in relation to the soil surface. Multiple devices from the hydrometeorological station's equipment can be analyzed, with the presence and explanations provided by specialists. It is essential to elucidate the

hydrometeorological phenomenon from the local to the national level through the processing of extensive data sets and their transmission to the central station in Chişinău.

Another objective proposed as a model for field applications could include the city of Ungheni, which holds a strategic geographic position for the Republic of Moldova. Students can access and learn about the Free Economic Zone within this urban settlement, from its inception to the present. They can explore the most important foreign economic agents present in the Free Economic Zone and the conditions for economic activity, including the involvement of local labor in the workforce, and more.

A production cycle of certain goods and consumer products can be carried out within the carpet factory and the ceramic factory by students. Other attractive objectives that can be subject to analysis include the railway bridge (Eiffel Bridge), which connects with the area across the Prut River. The train station in the city of Ungheni can serve as a railway hub, where students can familiarize themselves with the equipment used to change the gauge of train tracks between the Republic of Moldova and Romania.

Another objective of national importance that can be included in the field application is the visitation and exploration of the monastic complexes in Călăraşi county: Răciula, Hârbovăţ, Hârjauca, and Frumoasa. Their geographical position is remarkable as, when viewed from a height, they form an imaginary cross.

A distinctive objective that can be included in the practical route is the „Codru” balneoclimatic complex, with its functions of social and economic importance.

The time allocated for the analysis of the objectives described above can be scheduled over two days.

Another proposed objective for field applications could follow the following itinerary: Chişinău – Hânceşti – Leova – Cantemir – Cahul - Giurgiuleşti (Giurgiuleşti river port). The route may include stops in both urban and rural settlements. The agricultural landscapes analyzed differ from those in the central-western area, leaving their mark on predominantly steppe vegetation. Students can acquaint themselves with the landscapes of the Lower Prut, unlike those in the Middle Prut, through the complexity of analyzed floristic and faunistic species. A particularly attractive landscape is represented by Lake Manta, due to its immense surface and the human settlements in its immediate vicinity.

Another proposed objective for visiting is the village of Văleni with its oil wells (the only oil-related objective in the country). Giurgiuleşti Port is highlighted as a mandatory destination to visit as a Free Economic Zone, with the necessary explanations that can be provided by the port authorities. The priorities of direct access to the Danube River and, subsequently, the Black Sea can be explained to students by professors, emphasizing the economic advantages in terms of importing and exporting goods.

From the southernmost point, the itinerary follows the following route: Giurgiuleşti, Vulcăneşti, Taraclia, Ceadâr-Lunga, Comrat (Gagauzia UTA), Cimişlia, Hânceşti, Chişinău. Following the practical field application in complex geographical disciplines, students acquire skills to successfully analyze natural landscapes from a taxonomic perspective, as well as urban and rural anthropic landscapes, effectively combined with transportation landscapes (road, river, railway, and electric transport lines).

The processing of accumulated data takes place in laboratory conditions, highlighting the most important landscapes. The completion of field applications can be accompanied by the preparation of a poster that could reflect the entire field practice, from the initial phase to the final one.

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